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jmr&t
Journal of Materials Research and Technology
journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jmrt

Short Communication

A technical overview of metallic parts in hybrid additive manufacturing industry

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 19 September 2021

Accepted 18 February 2022

Available online 24 February 2022

Keywords:

Subtractive manufacturing

Additive manufacturing

Hybrid manufacturing

Artificial intelligence

Industry 4.0

ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing technologies have emerged as the promising alternatives of conventional manufacturing techniques. Conventional manufacturing techniques involves cutting and removal of material by mechanical procedures to achieve final product. Whereas, discrete chunks of material in any form are combined point by point and layer by layer for the fabrication of final product in additive manufacturing processes. Numerous advantages and inefficiencies of these manufacturing techniques are reflected in factors such as the design, fabrication, material properties and working condition etc. Therefore, development of a production technology by combining the benefits of both conventional and additive techniques is significantly important. “Hybrid Manufacturing” jointly apply additive and conventional production methods to attain final products. Hence, this short overview covers the operation aspects of both additive and subtractive manufacturing of metallic materials.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.02.085>

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Nomenclature	
AM	Additive manufacturing
MAM	Metal Additive manufacturing
WAAM	Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing
SLM	Selective Laser Melting
FEM	Finite element method
DED	Directed Energy Deposition
CNC	Computerized Numerical Control
CIRP	The International Academy of Production Engineering
MIG	Metal Inert Gas
TIG	Tungsten Inert Gas
HM	Hybrid Manufacturing
OD	outer diameter
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) techniques are being considered as the alternative of conventional manufacturing processes for the past couple of decades [1,2]. The rapid production of near net shape products of various materials is considered to be the main advantage that promote their application on mass scale [3]. Also, the ease of application of a single machine to fabricate a number of complex shapes and components that are otherwise difficult to be attained by individual conventional machining operations has been their selling point [4–6]. However, since AM techniques are now considered for mass production in several areas, new challenges are being observed rapidly and need to be contained and resolved to allow the current pace for AM [7,8]. The thin-walled structures, complex curved shapes and the lattice structures are among the prominent geometrical components that are preferred to be produced via AM techniques [9,10]. Due to high material losses, dimensional issues, the equipment constraints and the fabrication of inner cavities especially for the lattice structures, conventional manufacturing procedures present strict restrictions [11,12]. However, on the other hand, the production of these components via AM also have some restrictions and limitations. Achieving high accuracy and strict adherence to tolerance requirements are often not possible through AM due to the application of high-power heat sources [13,14]. Moreover, the material addition-based fabrication concept allows the addition of residual materials during fabrication [15,16]. On the other hand, subtractive machining procedures result in significantly high-quality products [17]. However for subtractive machining the geometrical conditions are not always favorable due to the geometrical complexity [18,19]. Therefore, a coupled application of both these procedures can create a superior manufacturing strategy. In this hybrid approach of both these techniques, additive manufacturing can create raw parts with near net shape geometrical and dimensional characteristics [20] whereas subtractive machining operations can be used to refine these raw parts to achieve the desired dimensional accuracy and surface finish [21]. Furthermore, the supporting

structures required for the fabrication of various complex components and the finishing post processing required are among the major issues of AM processes [22,23]. The support structures need to be removed after the production, which if done as a post processing increase the overall complexity and cost [24]. On the other hand, to remove the support structures the equipment restrictions associated with conventional procedures still remain. Similarly, for the thin-walled structures the material removal restrictions are also significant [25]. An appropriate alternative of separate AM or conventional manufacturing approaches is the hybrid additive manufacturing. Hybrid additive manufacturing can be defined as a process in which AM setup is coupled with a secondary energy source/tool that have the tendency synergically alter the process mechanics, part processing, quality and functionality. The common approach in hybrid additive manufacturing is to add a conventional subtractive process as the secondary process with deposition-based AM. A schematic diagram explaining the procedures and benefits of hybrid additive manufacturing procedure is also presented in Fig. 1. Whereas Table 1 provides an overview of some of the prominent hybrid manufacturing studies.

2. Operational research on hybrid manufacturing

2.1. Machining performance in hybrid manufacturing

Machining is a commonly adopted subtractive manufacturing method [38]. Unlike 3D printing, machining process starts with bulk material and continues by removing chips until the final shape is obtained as a result of relative movements between the cutting tool and bulk material [39,40] as can be seen in Fig. 2. Now a days, CNC machining is one of the most common approaches to fabricate components in various mechanical industries [41,42]. Although it is possible to obtain delicate features such as screw threads, precise holes, smooth edges and surfaces by machining, the huge material losses and large production time are the important disadvantages of this method [43].

3D printing on the other hand, is an additive manufacturing method in which two-dimensional sections of the final product on the print table/bed are added (Fig. 3) until final shape is obtained [44]. However, the size restrictions, material addition principles and suitable materials for various machines can also vary in 3D printing [45,46]. In addition to all these issues, the most important disadvantage of 3D printed components is the processing quality, especially high surface roughness and tolerances [47].

Considering the advantages and disadvantages together, a few simple principles can be drawn that can be applied to the decision-making process when choosing between 3D printing and machining. As a general rule, all parts that can be manufactured by additive manufacturing are generally suitable for machining [48]. For parts that are too complex to be produced by machining, such as topology-optimized geometries, it may be more appropriate to use additive manufacturing approaches [49]. 3D printing machine setups can be more economical than machining for manufacturing a small

Fig. 1 – (a) Schematic representation of metal removal processes at post-processing level (b) comparison of BTF ratios for a traditional metal removal process and a hybrid additive manufacturing process with material removal (copyrights reserved) [26].

number of parts or prototypes. Whereas, machining results in better surface quality, however it can be expensive while fabricating components in small batches. When a lot of parts need to be made (hundreds or more), neither machining nor 3D printing can be cost-effective options. Traditional forming technologies such as investment casting or injection molding stand out as the most economical option in such cases. As a result, hybrid manufacturing methods that eliminate the disadvantages of machining and additive manufacturing are a necessity [50,51].

2.2. Available machine setup for hybrid manufacturing

The International Academy of Production Engineering (CIRP) defines hybrid manufacturing as a combination of two or more manufacturing technologies in a new setup and using the advantages of each method in an integrated manner [52,53]. In other words, hybrid manufacturing involves the simultaneous application of different (chemical, physical, controlled) manufacturing principles on the same processing area [52]. In most hybrid manufacturing methods, additive manufacturing is used to make a near net shape component, followed by machining to refine the component and achieve desired finishing and tolerance requirements. For this purpose, some researchers have added a laser coating unit to conventional milling machines, combining the flexibility of laser coating processes and the high machining quality provided by milling operations as shown in Fig. 4. Using a 5-axis hybrid CNC machine, it is possible to manufacture complicated metal geometries using both DED and standard subtractive cutting. Laser heads can be automatically replaced as

spindle tools. As a result, design tweaks and alterations can be made at any point in the process. Compared to SLM, this is a huge advantage because SLM is physically unable to edit or modify an already-created part.

Jeng and Lin [55] used a hybrid fabrication process in which selective laser coating and milling processes were combined. In this setup, laser coating process creates the material layers, whereas milling process is used to adjust the coating height and to reduce the surface roughness. In addition, the effect of hybrid manufacturing was investigated by producing identical molds with only laser coating process. Nowotny et al. [56] proposed laser integration into machine tools as a new technical solution for repairs, rapid design changes and direct manufacturing of parts in a short time. They stated that hybrid manufacturing, which includes laser coating and machining, shortens the processing time, and produce different shapes effectively. Choi et al. [57] revealed the advantages and disadvantages of hybrid manufacturing in which wire welding technology and machining were used together. It was mentioned that CO₂ laser welding provides accurate deposition of metal material, while milling regulates the surface quality. The use of wire instead of powder in welding is advantageous in terms of a simple feed mechanism and a higher deposition rate. In this experimental study, process parameters such as laser power, welding speed, etc. were investigated as a function of microstructure, hardness and tensile strength. Gonzalez et al. [58] investigated the dimensional accuracy and surface roughness by manufacturing parts in various geometries with a hybrid system based on the integration of metal additive manufacturing, welding technology and CNC milling machines.

Table 1 – Overview of recent hybrid manufacturing investigations in recent past.

Refs #	Material	Technique	Machine	Outcomes	Author & Year
1	Ti6Al4V	WAAM + Forging	–	On forged preforms, wire-arc additive manufacturing produced these features, which met the mechanical qualities required for integration of both methods. In order to maximize material output and adaptability, new manufacturing chains can be designed using the combination of WAAM and forging.	Bambach et al., 2020 [27]
2	6511 Steel	SLM + Milling	Sodick OPM 250 L	Remaining compressive stress in the surface layer of an additive/subtractive hybrid manufacturing-produced sample was found to be substantially higher than that in the subsurface because of the martensitic transition.	Bai et al., 2020 [28]
3	15-5 P H	ASHM	FEM	It is suggested that a reduced cutting depth be employed first, followed by a reduced feed per tooth and finally an increased cutting speed, in order to prevent component deformation during the machining process.	Xie et al., 2020 [29]
4	316 L Steel	DED + Milling	DMG Lasertec 65	Controlling build height, dilution, and heat impacted zones can be achieved by adjusting laser power and powder flow rate, while maintaining travel speed and shielding gas flow. High dilution and higher heat affected zones occurred as a result of low powder flow rates, which increased the track height.	Nikolaos et al., 2020 [30]
5	ER2319 aluminum alloy	Laser + cold metal transfer	Fronius, CMT Advanced4000 R-Raycus, RFL-C3300W	Because of the arc and droplet impact force, the molten pool is sloping downwards. The molten metal is unable to reflux and solidify quickly because of the sudden drop in heat input.	Li et al., 2020 [31]
6	Al-Mg-Si Alloy 6061	The laser-arc + forming thin wall	GSI LUMONICS-Dynasty 200 DX	At the bottom, middle, and top, the microstructure is coarsely columnar, finely columnar, and finely equiaxed dendritic. Heat affected zones shrank as a result of the laser-affected zones with refining grains forming.	Liu et al., 2020 [32]

(continued on next page)

Table 1 – (continued)

Refs #	Material	Technique	Machine	Outcomes	Author & Year
7	ER2319 aluminum alloy	Laser + Tungsten Inert Gas	GSJJK701H pulsed laser	The mechanical properties of these specimens were superior to those of TIG, CMT, and SLM. With the smaller eutectics, more uniform distribution of copper ions, and semi-coherent ' phases, we were able to increase performance. Material can be used in many different ways when it is combined with laser and arc technology to manufacture components with exceptional mechanical properties.	Wu et al., 2020 [33]
8	Hastelloy X	Plasma-rotating-electrode process + Directed Energy Deposition	–	In less time, custom products are manufactured depending on the required strength. Applicable also to the production of a conceptual model to accelerate the development and research process.	Guo et al., 2020 [34]
9	316 Stainless steels	Coupling milling	Optomec LENS Hybrid Machine Tool	One milling operation may accomplish both surface finish and quality assessment in one milling process using the proposed technique, which fills a measure gap in hybrid additive manufacturing.	Avegnon et al., 2021 [35]
10	316 Stainless steels	Coin minting by AM+ and forming	DMG Mori Lasertec 30SLM	The novel designs incorporated in the additively made coin blanks enable the production of unique collector coins that are significantly more valuable than those now accessible.	Pragana et al., 2020 [36]
11	316 Stainless steels	Directed energy deposition process + Laser remelting process	Fronius TPS 5000 arc power Source + IPG YLS-10000 laser device	The surface quality and corrosion resistance of a remelting layer can be improved by increasing laser remelting power, but microhardness of the remelting layer can be degraded due to a decrease in the number of phases.	Chen et al., 2020 [37]

2.3. Current trends in hybrid manufacturing

Song and Park [59] investigated various design parameters of hybrid fabrication using a combination of welding technology and milling. They presented alternative approaches for the manufacture of tin and zinc alloyed stainless steel by making changes to the welding gun and other welding parameters. Kapil et al. [60] used various combinations of hybrid fabrication method in which MIG, TIG welding and laser coating technology were combined with 3-axis CNC in the turbine blade fabrication. The efficiency of the production with this developed hybrid manufacturing method is significantly high

in comparison with the production with traditional methods. Suryakumar et al. [61] investigated the production parameters of hybrid fabrication consisting of welding and milling processes numerically and experimentally. The economy of the production model they developed for welding has been proven for injection molds and has been developed for hybrid manufacturing. Xiang et al. [62], on the other hand, solved the problems of insufficient dimensional accuracy and surface quality with the hybrid system they used together with plasma arc welding and machining. Lanzetta and Cutkosky [63] created smooth shaped products of dry adhesives that can be used to assist human and robotic climbing with a

Fig. 2 – Subtractive manufacturing.

Fig. 3 – Additive manufacturing (3D printing).

combination of shape deposition fabrication and stock removal. Ruan et al. [64] developed an algorithm for a five-axis laser-assisted manufacturing process (LAMP) and fabricated various parts with uniform and non-uniform thicknesses. As shown in Fig. 5, the LAMP manufacturing process incorporates a powder-fed laser deposition technique as well as a 5-axis computer numerically controlled machining system. The

Fig. 4 – Machine setup for Hybrid manufacturing (copyrights reserved) [54].

laser scanning of the powder bed is followed by a milling operation to produce the final shape of the components. The newly developed algorithms in the planning of the manufacturing process helped the hybrid system in configuring parts more efficiently.

Research, development and system integration with hybrid fabrication to produce high-temperature materials was presented by Liou et al. [66]. Hur et al. [67] came up with an approach to combine the advantages of rapid prototyping setup with high precision of CNC machines. An ultrasonic-based micro powder feeding mechanism was used to make very small patterns of powders that are sintered with a very small laser beam.

The structure between property, mechanism, energy and hybrid manufacturing process is given in Fig. 6. Figure 6 illustrates a method that widens the range of processes that can be considered, but also relates the processes to the final material and part qualities by using the governing physical mechanisms that govern each of them. For example, it outlines the materials design aspects of hybrid-AM while also highlighting how new processes and materials can be developed in tandem.

3. Quality aspects of hybrid manufacturing

Hybrid manufacturing is currently a developing field which consists of all those manufacturing approaches where different operations are collectively applied on a single machine setup. The adaptation of the hybrid manufacturing is mainly governed by the high surface finish and dimensional requirements. The quality in terms of surface finish and dimensional accuracy has been investigated for hybrid manufacturing by a number of researchers. Andrew et al. [69] stated two sub steps based sequential hybrid manufacturing and iterative hybrid manufacturing approaches for the fabrication of a titanium component. With the adaptation of iterative approach, the component was successfully achieved with a total time of 15 h and ease of fabrication for difficult inner geometrical features along with an excellent surface deviation of 9 μm . It was found that the AM as built surface of 316 L steel was rough due to the adhesion of unmelted powder particles. The HM's surface, on the other hand, was relatively smooth. Furthermore, several irregular microstructural characteristics were found in hybrid manufactured parts which didn't undergo the thermal treatments. These irregular microstructural features were mainly due to the extremely high cooling rates involved in AM. The irregular and non-equilibrium microstructures were also found to be eliminated and replaced by characteristic austenite phase structures for the HM part subjected to heat treatment [70]. Regarding the influence of machining parameters on final surface quality in hybrid manufacturing, it was observed that spindle speed has the most prominent influence on surface roughness in comparison with material removal area or federate [71]. Moreover, higher spindle speeds were reported to be significant in enhancing the surface quality as well as decreasing the geometrical accuracy requirements in HM. A moderate feed rate on the other hand was found to be better in order to attain a better agreement between the surface quality

Fig. 5 – Schematic diagram of (a) Pre-heat laser assisted cutting; (b) Pre-heat laser assisted grinding (copyrights reserved) [65].

and the efficiency [71]. Li et al. [72] proposed a hybrid WAAM and milling based framework and investigated the fabrication of aerospace grade stiffened panels. Through the optimization, it was depicted that a high movement speed, a target width dependent wire-feed rate, a high spindle speed, and a moderate tool-feed rate are essential in attaining a better coupled influence on surface quality, low material usage and efficiency. Therefore, in order to select approximate process parameters for hybrid manufacturing processes it can serve as a criterion. Nikolaos et al. [30] also observed the post milling surface finish of DED made 316 L stainless steel in hybrid manufacturing. The surface condition was found to be much

worse by up milling due to adhered chips. It was also observed that the skin layer of the material is more machinable than the bulk material. The tool life was also observed and found to be significantly improved by down milling. Bojing et al. [34] observed the tensile and hardness behavior of different regions for a hybrid manufacturing approach. Hastelloy X based component showed elevated hardness values at the interface regions. Similarly, the strength values were also elevated but a decrease in the ductility was found as well. Similarly, Wei et al. [73] also reported the hardness values for an additive subtractive made 18 Ni 300 steel. The hardness values of the hybrid manufacturing fabricated components were high in

Fig. 6 – Structure between "Property – mechanism – energy – hybrid manufacturing process" (copyrights reserved) [68].

Fig. 7 – Representation of a typical stress distribution and what happens to ID readings when material is removed from the outer diameter (OD). A) hoop stress, B) axial stress (copyrights reserved) [74].

comparison with the SLM made samples. The post machining surface roughness values on the other hand were found to be lower for SLM made components in comparison with the

wrought samples for all the considered feed rates. Overall, it was found that the hybrid manufactured components had better performance and output. Jarred et al. [74] also observed the residual stress and distortion as a result of multiple fabrication processes applied subsequently i.e., hybrid manufacturing. Figure 7 shows that the residual stress in the as built cylindrical components was primarily tensile in the outer material and compressive for inner material. Whereas it was observed that during the post fabrication machining phase the cylindrical samples contracted during the outer diameter machining operation. Therefore, it was suggested that cutting conditions induce compressive stresses along the outer surface.

4. Future prospects in hybrid manufacturing

4.1. AI and intelligent components applications in hybrid manufacturing

In the hybrid manufacturing method being able to foresee the results, whether in design or production, is extremely important. Efforts are underway to achieve the most efficient work with the least material wastage with imaging programs or simulation techniques. This is one of the points where artificial intelligence and hybrid manufacturing can be combined. The use of artificial intelligence in hybrid manufacturing is a step that will provide great convenience in optimization. In future, hybrid manufacturing will find lots of solutions with AI technology (Fig. 8) for a designed model be as efficient as it is in theory. Artificial intelligence and software development are causing huge impacts on future businesses and the end consumer market. The 'Airbus' company uses most of the parts for airplanes designed and manufactured with Hybrid Manufacturing. Almost all engineering materials can also be used as base materials for Hybrid Manufacturing.

4.2. Industry 4.0 and hybrid manufacturing

The build-up of part-integrations of intelligent systems is essential to meet future challenges of "Industry 4.0," like the customization of goods, lifecycle data, and real-time

Fig. 8 – Hybrid manufacturing with AI technology (copyrights reserved) [75].

Fig. 9 – The power plant concept for structural monitoring of the turbine blade integrated with the sensor (copyrights reserved) [76].

monitoring of engineering systems. Sensors and actuators are therefore key elements in order to control the industry value chain globally and intelligently.

With traditional manufacturing or forming processes, it's almost impossible to put mechatronic devices inside of a component in a way that makes it structurally sound. However, with additive manufacturing, this can be achieved due to the layer-by-layer manufacturing approach. This allows the fabrication of intelligent structures, which could be a big change in the way CI is made in the future [76]. For sensor integration via additive manufacturing, various industrial purposes can be identified: Specifically for medical purposes, advanced biomechanical devices can be manufactured with a fully enclosed RFID tag [77] for the personalization. In order to improve stability, for example, sensor data can adapt the connectivity of implants and ossic structures [78]. Furthermore, integrated sensors may be used to predict maintenance of machine tools [79] and to monitor wear and temperature for metal-forming tools [80]. Mechatronic components for on-site damage detection and life estimate can be used in many areas of lightweight design, including the energy sector. This results in a reconfiguration of the light part with regard to weight and critical load path. For instance, Fig. 9 shows the power plant concept for structural monitoring of the turbine blade integrated with the sensor. The capability of the wing to continuously monitor mechanical and temperature loads with sensors near to the critical locations benefits from the maximum temperature and increases efficiency of the system.

In 2001, Li was responsible for the preliminary work on embedded sensors in layered metal components through the hybrid manufacturing in metal doped components of fiber optical sensors and fiber bragg grating (FBG) sensors. In addition, Mathew presented the integration of FBGs and several research groups investigated the use of fiber optic sensors [81]. Moreover, thin-film sensors, RFID chips and DC motors or piezo actuators [82] and Stoll's temperature sensors [83] have been studied for their application areas. The common point of the preliminary studies is that each integrated electronic component has its own design or integration concept that is tailored to the component [84].

5. Conclusions

A generic hybridization process that is compatible with 3D metal printing methods such as CPA, SLM, and SLS should be developed. Adhesive production technologies are becoming more powerful and diverse in terms of processing capacity, materials, and applications. In order to use the advantages of both approaches, a hybrid manufacturing method must be developed. Current hybrid approaches for shape deposition fabrication are not viable for powder bed technology as they will damage the untreated powders and make subsequent layers impossible. In addition, some additive manufacturing technologies such as EBM work in high vacuum conditions, so it is not appropriate to manage the machine tools in the similar conditions. These types of additive manufacturing methods can only process materials such as super alloys or have better metallurgical properties due to the environmental conditions. As a result, a new hybrid approach is required that does not depend on a specific additive manufacturing method and can address any additive manufacturing method.

Hybrid methods combine machining and additive manufacturing to produce parts with difficult-to-machine materials while maintaining tight tolerances and high surface quality. As the “click-to-print” methodology of additive manufacturing, the hybrid approach to be developed should not need special fixture and tool depending on the part design and should be able to work with minimum human interventions and skills. Finally, the hybrid approach should be able to be applied without any adaptation to the existing additive manufacturing method. Thus, a hybrid approach will be achieved in which the advantageous aspects of additive manufacturing and machining methods can be obtained together.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

The work presented in this paper is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, original, except as acknowledged in the text, and the material has not been submitted, either in whole or in part, for a degree at this or any other university. There is no conflict of interest to declare.

Acknowledgement

The research is supported by the Regional Operational Programme for the Opole Voivodeship financed by the Structural Funds of the European Union and the State budget of Poland, RPOP.01.01.00-16-0015/17.

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